

Deliverable Document 1

On-site computing software and hardware architecture recommendation

E3DDS Team *

January 23, 2019

Date	Comments
2018/06/19	First draft started
2018/12/07	Reviewed by Anders
2018/12/17	Sent to SG

*Anders Tjulin (EISCAT) anders.tjulin@eiscat.se; Ari Lukkarinen (CSC) ari.lukkarinen@csc.fi; Assar Westman (EISCAT) Assar.Westman@eiscat.se; Carl-Fredrik Enell (EISCAT) carl-fredrik.enell@eiscat.se; Dan Johan Jonsson (UiT) dan.jonsson@uit.no; Janos Nagy (NSC) fconagy@nsc.liu.se; Harri Hellgren (EISCAT) harri@eiscat.se; Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT) ingemar.haggstrom@eiscat.se; Mattias Wadenstein (UmU) maswan@hpc2n.umu.se; Roy Dragseth (UiT) roy.dragseth@uit.no; John White (NeIC) john.white@cern.ch

Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Purpose	3
3	Introduction	3
4	On-site hardware	5
4.1	First Stage Receive Unit rates	8
4.1.1	Skibotn site:	8
4.1.2	Receive sites	8
4.2	Input network	8
4.3	Ring Buffer	10
4.4	Second beam former rates	12
4.5	On-site local disk buffer	14
4.6	Additional servers for services	14
4.7	Output network	14
5	On-site software	15
5.1	Receiver and ring buffer process	16
5.2	Second level beam former	16
5.3	File writer and prompt computing	16
5.4	Control	17
	Appendix A Cost estimate	19
	Appendix B Future outlook	21

1 Executive Summary

The on-site computing, network and storage needs for the EISCAT_3D transmitting and receiving sites have been discussed and calculated to not vary much from initial estimates.

There are two possible choices of input network architecture between the First Stage Receiving Units to the second beam former: a switch fabric or direct connections from FSRUs to second beam-former servers. A comparative pricing for each option is included. Discussions including networking experts and FSRU manufacturer have concluded that the optimal output connections are 2×25 Gb/s optical.

The second beam former is presently calculated to require 40 2U server nodes for real-time FIR filtering at 5 MHz bandwidth rates. The FIR filter outputs must also be summed in realtime at 5 MHz bandwidth. Either more 2U server nodes need to be added to accommodate the summation or a high-performance switching fabric downstream of the server nodes will perform the summations.

The processes that write the summed second beam former results to files are proposed to run on the second beam former servers OR on dedicated servers downstream but before the site-local buffer.

The optimum configuration for the site-local buffer is proposed to be RAID-5 SSDs directly integrated to the second beam former nodes. This is instead of the first-proposed separate disk array.

2 Purpose

This document describes and recommends the on-site computing software and hardware architectures for EISCAT_3D. These recommendations are the outcome of iterative discussions between the EISCAT_3D software engineers and scientists and national provider deployment experts. The architecture is a result of close discussions and work between the on-site computing (beam former, Level 2 data processing, Level 3 data analysis and possibly satellite screening code) developers, EISCAT scientists and the operators of the national e-infrastructures. This document describes the prototype software to be written and gives the software and hardware recommendations.

The target readers of this document are primarily the EISCAT_3D project management and scientists. The EISCAT_3D project management can get an indication of the actual amount of computing at the different EISCAT_3D sites. Also, another target is the providers of the national e-infrastructures where EISCAT_3D will be located. The national e-infrastructure providers can see the quantity and type of computing required for EISCAT_3D and make determinations whether some can be run in existing computing centres.

3 Introduction

The EISCAT Scientific Association will establish EISCAT_3D, a flexible multistatic high power radar system, that will enable comprehensive three-dimensional vector observations of the atmosphere and ionosphere above Northern Fenno-Scandinavia.

The use of new radar technology, combined with the latest advances within digital signal processing, will achieve ten times higher temporal and spatial resolution than obtained by the present EISCAT radar systems. For the first time, EISCAT will also be able to measure continuously. The flexibility of the EISCAT_3D system will enable scientists to investigate upper-atmospheric and ionospheric phenomena at both large and small scales unobtainable by the present systems.

In its first stage, the EISCAT_3D system will consist of three radar sites: one having both **T**ransmitting (**TX**) and **R**eceiving (**RX**) capabilities and two with only RX capability. The sites will be remote-controlled and located in three different countries (Finland, Norway and Sweden) and will be separated geographically by approximately 130 km. Two additional receiver sites, at distances 200-250 km from the transmit site, are planned for the full EISCAT_3D system at a later stage.

EISCAT_3D will produce data at three levels, from raw samples to physical parameters. Table 1 summarizes the EISCAT_3D data levels. This data will be curated, archived and catalogued. This

Level	Type	Produced by	Storage	Format
1a	Ring buffer data	1 st stage beam former	4 months*	UDP stream/ HDF5
1b	Beam-formed data	2 nd stage beam former	4 months*	HDF5
2	Time integrated correlated data	All sites	Archived	HDF5
3a	Physical parameters	All sites	Archived	HDF5
3b	3D-voxel parameters	Operations centre	Archived	HDF5
4	Derived geophysical parameters	Users	Users	Publications etc

Table 1: Summary of the EISCAT_3D data levels. The EISCAT_3D data centres will receive, serve and archive all data at levels 2 and 3. Data used in research should be given Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) according to a common standard such as DOI, DataCite, or similar, to be unambiguously citable in publications. (*) A 4 months period is selected as this is the estimated time required to perform a “real-time” analysis on low-level data. A portion of the level 1 data will also be archived permanently, on the order of 1% of the level 1 data rate, e.g. one beam per site and/or bandwidth-limited data.

encompasses the management of the data throughout its lifecycle, from initial storage to the time when it is moved to long-term preservation for posterity or becomes obsolete and is deleted. Metadata will be produced according to standardized metadata models and transferred to search portals.

Also, for scientific publications using EISCAT_3D data, a system to cite the data sets used should be provided in compliance with recommendations from funding agencies and the EU (FAIR principles are gaining importance: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Scientific work using and visualizing EISCAT_3D data, or deriving other physical parameters by combining EISCAT_3D data with other data, represents a fourth level. Derived data products produced by EISCAT_3D users are indicated as Level 4 in the table, in addition to the three data levels produced by EISCAT_3D.

The first stage receive unit attached to each sub-array (Fig. 1) produces voltage-domain data from 10 wide-angle beams as a series of data (level 1a) as a UDP bit-stream. These data are buffered on the site RAM ring buffer and may be buffered for 4 months on the operations centre storage. Likewise, the narrow angle beam files (level 1b) from the second beam former are buffered for 4 months on the operations centre storage. A fraction (dependent on the experiment being performed) of the first and second stage beam formed data will be stored as persistent level 1 data files and sent to the data centres.

From the level 1b data, it will be possible to generate *lag profiles* (level 2 data), i.e. transform the data to the autocorrelation function domain. This is equivalent to power spectra, and thus the volume of level 2 data can be reduced by time averaging. Physical parameters (level 3a data) will also be extracted by means of an inverse incoherent scatter model. The level 2 and 3a data from the three sites will be combined to produce level 3b data products: three-dimensional volume renderings of both scalar parameters and velocity vectors.

The data will be buffered at the sites or / and a central storage and then transferred to the data centres for long-term storage and access. The provisioned container format of the data received at the data centres from the operations centre is HDF5 [1] (a standard data container library available for all considered programming languages). HDF5 based file formats are used by other radar systems such as AMISR ¹ and Millstone Hill (https://github.com/MITHaystack/digital_rf).

4 On-site hardware

Figure 1 gives the schematic representation of the data flow within a RX (or receiving on the TX) site from the antenna sub-array first beam former to the local site storage.

The **F**irst **S**tage **R**eceiving **U**nit (FSRU) (FSRU_s where $s = 1, 109$ ²) attached to each of the site sub-arrays are shown at the top of Figure 1. Each FSRU outputs 10 wide-angle beams that are transmitted as UDP data packets ($b_s^n_p$) where $s = 1, 109$ is the sub-array number, $n = 1, 10$ is the wide-angle beam number and $p = a, b$ is the polarization of the beam. The FSRUs are either directly connected to the computing nodes that contain the RAM ring buffer, or there is a switch that directs the UDP packets to the appropriate nodes. The packets are written to the ring buffer ordered by beam number and polarization with all sub-array packets as a sequence $\{b_1^1_a, \dots, b_{109}^1_a\}, \{b_1^1_b, \dots, b_{109}^1_b\}, \{b_1^2_a, \dots, b_{109}^2_a\}, \dots$, etc of 2180 ($109 \times 10 \times 2$) wide-angle beams.

Each second beam former FIR filtering operations handles one beam from each sub-array for a total of 21800 filtering operations. The outputs of the filter operations are summed to produce up to 200 narrow-angle (0.6° wide) beams ³ (B_p^m where $m = 1, 10$ and $p = a, b$) transmitted to file writers. The summed beams are written as files (one beam per file) to the local site storage.

¹Craig Heinselman, internal communication

²There are 109 sub-arrays on the RX sites and 119 sub-arrays on the TX site.

³The full EISCAT_3D design specification will produce 100 narrow angle beams per polarization for a total of 200.

Figure 1: Schematic of the on-site data flow from the sub-arrays to site storage.

Figure 2: Overview of the site computing hardware including control and analysis hardware. The various site clusters are connected by high-speed network e.g. Infiniband.

4.1 First Stage Receive Unit rates

A general description of the **F**irst **S**tage **R**eceiving **U**nit (FSRU) units can be found in [2]. Development has started and the final design will be ready by February 2019. There will be one FSRU per sub-array having 182 analog channels from 91 antennas. After analog-to-digital conversion, signals are delayed and combined to form 10 wide angle beams having two polarizations each.

The original design was to use 100 Gb/s links from each FSRU to the cluster computer, but the possibility to use two 25 Gb/s optical links instead has been studied and proposed to the FSRU supplier.

One 25 Gb/s link cannot deliver the required data rates of the full 30 MHz bandwidth and 10 beams.

4.1.1 Skibotn site:

Table 2 gives the total data rate from all sub-array first beam-formers at the Skibotn TX site. For the 5 MHz “continuous” operation there will be 2 beams per FSRU, each FSRU will transmit 0.6 Gb/s. The the total data rate from all sub-arrays to the ring buffer in 5 MHz bandwidth will be 76 Gb/s.

For the 30 MHz bandwidth mode, anticipated to run only in a “burst” mode, there are 1 or 2 beams per FSRU over all the 119 sub-arrays as, by definition, the radar TX and RX directions are along the same line of site at the TX station. As the 5 MHz and 30 MHz bandwidths are operated simultaneously, the total data rate is summed to produce 0.54 Tb/s.

Band-width	Beams /FSRU	Bits × Polarities	Rate /FSRU	Sub-arrays	Total rate
5 MHz	2	(16+16)×2	0.6 Gb/s	119	0.08 Tb/s
30 MHz	2	(16+16)×2	3.8 Gb/s	119	0.46 Tb/s

Table 2: Total data rates expected at the Skibotn TX site.

4.1.2 Receive sites

Table 3 gives the total data rate from all sub-array first beam-formers at the receive sites. For 5 MHz bandwidth “continuous” operation there are 10 beams per FSRU, each FSRU will transmit 3.2 Gb/s for a total rate to the ring buffer of 0.35 Tb/s (350 Gb/s to be compared to 76 Gb/s on the TX site). For the 30 MHz bandwidth mode, anticipated to run only in a “burst” mode, 2 beams will be used per sub-array. In the 30 MHz bandwidth case, the 30 MHz and 5 MHz rates are summed for a total of 0.76 Tb/s of UDP stream data sent to the ring buffer.

4.2 Input network

The input network delivers the 2180 UDP streams through either 2×25 Gb/s or 1×100 Gb/s interfaces per first stage receive unit (109 or 119 depending on site) through fiber optic links from

Band-width	Beams /FSRU	Bits \times Polarities	Rate /FSRU	Sub-arrays	Total rate
5 MHz	10	$(16+16)\times 2$	3.2 Gb/s	109	0.35 Tb/s
30 MHz	2	$(16+16)\times 2$	3.84 Gb/s	109	0.41 Tb/s

Table 3: Total data rates expected at the receive sites.

Figure 3: Input network that assumes 2x25 Gb/s optical connections from each FSRU directly connected to the second beam former nodes.

each first stage receive unit to the n server nodes that contain the RAM ring buffer. These are the same nodes that perform the second level beam forming: the name second beam former node and ring buffer node are interchangeable. There is a choice between connecting the first stage receive unit links directly to “ n ” ring buffer (or second beam former) nodes as shown in Figure 3 or have a switching fabric in between, as shown in Figure 4.

The advantages of a direct connection of the first stage receive unit links is that the loss of a single component will only result in a fractional loss of $1/n$ of the inputs, which results in lower resolution but still judged to be usable data for $n > 10$. It also puts constraints on the “ n ” ring buffer nodes since each must provide $238/n$ 25 Gb/s interfaces, in addition to an internal communications fabric between the ring buffer nodes and a normal interface for exporting data products and system management. A quick market survey has put the upper limit on the number of useful 25 Gb/s interfaces per 2U server at 12 or 13.

A switching fabric (shown in Figure 4) allows flexible fail-over through the ability to switch any first stage receive unit to any ring buffer node, which is helpful from a reliability point of view, as we can assume that server nodes will need scheduled maintenance or will have unscheduled failures. Recovery from this situation in a fully switched network situation with at least one spare ($n+1$) ring buffer node can be done in milliseconds, compared to hours or days if someone has to travel to a remote site. Having a unique destination IP and unique port for each first level beam is also

convenient for the software solution.

Switching also means that the ring buffer nodes only need one 100 Gb/s interface per node for the incoming data, and thus more compact servers are possible.

The downside is the extra cost for switches and that the switch itself will be a single point of failure that can stop a site.

Figure 4: Input network candidate that assumes 2x25 Gb/s optical connections from each FSRU to a layer 3 switching infrastructure. A earlier option uses a single 100 Gb/s optical connection to the switching infrastructure.

4.3 Ring Buffer

The ring buffer is a pool of fast-access storage (DRAM, Flash, Phase-Change memory, etc) that is integral to the SBF nodes. The beam data packets ($b_s^n_p$) from the FSRU are written to the ring buffer memory. The ring buffer size is based on the baseline 5 MHz bandwidth operation and is sized for the time that level-1b data can be written to the storage to be processed off-line or written to the disk buffer.

The minimum ring buffer should allow 100 s of 5 MHz bandwidth data to be stored, e.g. in order to search for meteors and space debris in the raw data. An upper limit on the ring buffer capacity is to store 1200 s of 30 MHz data, which is required to cover a typical scientific rocket launch with F-region (around 250 km) apogee and calculate posterior beams along the trajectory (Nickolay Ivchenko, KTH, Stockholm, private communication). If trajectory data could be obtained

in near real time (few minutes), this requirement would be relaxed accordingly as the desired beams could then also be formed with a delay on the order of some minutes. The following tables give the calculations for the ring buffer based on an assumption that the ring buffer must accommodate a minimum of 100 s of real-time 5 MHz level-1a data and up to the maximum of 1200 s.

The buffer calculations for the Skibotn transmitting and receiving site are shown in Table 4. These calculations assume that in the 5 MHz mode, the site produces only 2 wide-angle beams (along the current and preceding transmission beams). In the 30 MHz mode, there are additionally 2 beams.

Bandwidth	Beams/ FSRU	Bits \times Polarity \times Subarrays	Total rate (Tb/s)	Buffer 5 MHz (s)	Buffer size (TB)	Buffer 30 MHz (s)
5 MHz	2	(16+16) $\times 2$ $\times 119$	0.08	100 400	1.0 3.8	15 56
30 MHz			0.46	1200	11.4	169

Table 4: Ring buffer calculations and buffer time for 30 MHz bandwidth operation at Skibotn. The buffer time for the 30 MHz operations is based on the assumption that there are simultaneously 2 beams each of 5 MHz and 30 MHz.

The buffer calculations for the receiving sites are shown in Table 5. These calculations assume that in the 5 MHz mode, the sites produce 10 wide-angle beams. In the 30 MHz mode, the sites produce 8-wide-angle beams at 5 MHz and 2 wide-angle beams at 30 MHz.

Bandwidth	Beams/ FSRU	Bits \times Polarity \times Subarrays	Total rate (Tb/s)	Buffer 5 MHz (s)	Buffer size (TB)	Buffer 30 MHz (s)
5 MHz	10	(16+16) $\times 2$ $\times 109$	0.35	100 400	4.4 17.5	51 203
30 MHz	2		0.41	1200	52.5	609

Table 5: Ring buffer calculations and buffer time for 30 MHz bandwidth operation at the RX sites. The buffer time for the 30 MHz operations is based on the assumption that there are simultaneously 8 beams at 5 MHz and 2 beams at 30 MHz.

As can be seen in the above Tables 4 and 5, the time that data can be written into the ring buffer when the 30 MHz mode is in operation is roughly an order of magnitude less time at the Skibotn site and half the time at the receive sites. This is due to the time requirements (min 100 s and max 1200 s) for the ring buffer in the 5 MHz mode. A consequence is that the size (physical) of the ring buffer on the Skibotn and receive sites will be different.

The 30 MHz bandwidth is mainly for astronomy and plasma line search (including NEIALs⁴ with plasma lines). The system will be switched to the high 30 MHz rate when NEIALs are detected, and in this case run the FSRUS at 30 MHz for an interval up to about an hour, overwriting the ring buffer in 10 s intervals and storing those with detected NEIALS to disk for offline interferometry. The time to write level 1 (a or b) data from the ring buffer memory to the disk buffer must be considered also. Writing the level 1a data out to a spinning hard disk buffer will be at least one order of magnitude slower than receiving it from the FSRUs (depending on the storage bandwidth capacity of the site local buffer).

An option for writing level 1a data in burst mode is to use local Solid State Drives (SSDs) i.e. SSDs installed in the ring buffer nodes. SSDs that can handle up to 2-3 Drive Writes Per Day cost much less than RAM, probably adding only 5-10 percent to the ring buffer costs. This means the 30 MHz data could be flushed from the ring buffer in only 2-4 times as long as it took to receive from the source and enable rapid resumption of 5 MHz operations. This is under the assumption that 30 MHz burst mode with raw data dumping would not occur more than 2-3 times per day on a long term average.

4.4 Second beam former rates

The **Second Beam Former** (SBF) consists of **F**inite **I**mpulse **R**esponse (FIR) filters. The output of the SBF is 10 narrow angle beams per polarity, with a design possible to scale to 100 narrow angle beams per polarity. Each output beam uses data from one wide angle beam on each first stage receive unit so that each narrow angle beam, B_a^2 , is a summation of data from FIR filters acting on $b_{1a}^2 \dots b_{109a}^2$

The beamforming thus requires $109 \times 2 \times 10 \times 10 = 21800$ FIR filters in total. From the note at [3] this implies a processing power of 13380 GFLOPS to process 5 MHz data in real time. Benchmarks from [3] has put the performance of modern CPUs at roughly up to 600 GFLOPS per dual CPU node. This leads to a minimum requirement of some 40 2U servers in the second beam former at the RX sites. The number of SBF nodes required for the CPU part of the beam forming is expected to change downwards as the optimization and testing of the beam forming code proceeds. At the TX (Skibotn) site, the number of input wide angle beams at 5 MHz is 2 vs 10 which implies a reduction in the required computing capacity by a factor of 5, giving 8 2U nodes.

After the FIR filters the data have to be summed, which aggregates to a large data rate. For a naive implementation of just sending all the data for each narrow angle beam to a destination node for summation, a 200 Gb/s network fabric would be needed for the summation alone. By summing the values from more than 15 wide angle beams within each node, a 100 Gb/s network will be adequate.

Currently, as explained in [3] (Section 2.3.1), the summation of the beams within the test servers of the SBF nodes encounters a memory bottleneck that lowers the overall processing speed. Using the benchmark for the summation within the SBF nodes would imply that the number of SBF nodes

⁴Naturally Enhanced Ion-Acoustic Lines, an asymmetry in the scatter spectrum.

Figure 5: The creation of 10 narrow angle beams (in polarity “a”) through FIRs and summation, showing how each output beam needs input from one beam from each subarray

would need to increase. An current estimate from [3] increases the number of 2U nodes by a factor of 1.5.

A high-performance interconnect such as Infiniband [4] or Omni-Path [5] with a focus on parallel computation and low overhead RDMA is suggested to leave as much CPU power as possible in the SBF nodes for the necessary calculations. For Infiniband there is also the intriguing possibility of

using functionality in the network switch to do the summation inside the switch instead of in the nodes. An important design point for this network component is that single switches have 36, 40, or possibly 80 ports. But since the cross-node summation only needs to happen within one polarization, splitting the nodes over two switches is fine and more than 72 nodes in total should hopefully not be needed.

4.5 On-site local disk buffer

After the narrow angle beams are summed in the ring buffer nodes, the data streams need to be ordered into files and then shipped off site to a data center for permanent storage. In order to handle short interruptions and the occasional inefficient scheduling, a local buffer of at least a few minutes and preferably a few hours is needed.

The total output of the second level beam former is $32 + 32 \text{ bits} \times 200 \text{ beams} \times 5 \text{ MHz} = 8 \text{ GB/s}$ at 5 MHz operations. As mentioned in Section 4.3 the ring buffer (or SBF) nodes can be equipped with SSDs. For example, six 400 GB SSDs in a raid 5 configuration provide 2 TB net usable buffer space, which turns into 250 seconds or $n \times 6$ minutes of effective buffer space in the 5 MHz case, and a sixth of that for 30 MHz (30 MHz will (can)not be beam formed in real time on the available compute resources though). This would also be a fast (2–4 GB/s on each node) target for saving sections of the ring buffer, where speed of writing is important to free up that part of the ring buffer for new data.

Using Non-Volatile Memory express (NVMe) for these SSDs might add a bit of cost (list prices are 1.2 times more expensive) but indications are that in a competitive tender the difference is not so big. Also NVMe reduces CPU usage for I/O and increases total speed.

4.6 Additional servers for services

Operations of the experiment and maintenance tasks for the computing requires a highly available database as well as several servers to handle orchestration, software maintenance tasks, file transfer scheduling, etc. A system to run highly available databases and virtual machines could echo the one used by the NeIC NT1, and need three physical hosts with local storage.

For maximum commonality, three more nodes with the same specification of the SBF nodes would be appropriate. As a compromise to reduce the cost, they could be ordered with significantly less RAM (200–300 GB) and only 2 or 4 network interfaces.

4.7 Output network

The data produced in the SBF, control updates, as well as general remote management requires connectivity to the datacenter (and directly or indirectly the internet). The wide area network connectivity will provide one 100 Gb/s network link. This should be connected to one (or several) switches that have enough ports to connect to all the SBF nodes as well as the VM hosts at 10 or 25 Gb/s. Such a switch could be a $48 \times 25 + 6 \times 100$ Gb/s switch.

If redundancy here is needed, it could be possible to have two switches in active/passive mode, but this would add both cost and complexity while the expected failure rate of quality networking equipment is generally very low. Two switches with any kind of automatic or remote failover capability would also mean two interfaces on every host and in the wide area router. If any manual re-cabling is required in the event of a output network switch failure then ideally there will be a spare unit at the Skibotn TX site and one at the EISCAT headquarters in Kiruna. The RX sites in Sweden and Finland are reachable by car within 2 hours from Kiruna, Skibotn is 4 hours.

5 On-site software

Figure 6: A schematic view of the different software components of the second beam former.

5.1 Receiver and ring buffer process

A suggested design is to run a process (the ring buffer process) for each first level wide-angle beam, that listens to a dedicated port and puts all the received data into a ring buffer in the shared memory of the server node. The process reads the data stream index number from the data packet header and updates the ring buffer database table so that received data can be associated with corresponding data stream.

Once a predefined number of data packets from all sub-arrays have been written to the ring buffer, the process triggers the second beam former FIR filter process dedicated to this first level beam.

The ring buffer keeps the data so that in case post-analyzer process finds an interesting event, the corresponding data can be marked as protected and to be downloaded separately. This will be done in a database table. These ring buffer areas will not be used for new data until they are released by higher level control (i.e. after the data is downloaded to the local buffer).

5.2 Second level beam former

A second beam former process with correct delay and decimation values is implemented when experiment is formed. The second beam former process is executed by the ring buffer when enough data have been received. Data stream index and location of the data are given as parameters.

The second beam former process copies samples to 10 different data flows and runs a FIR filter algorithm through the data. The result is 10 different narrow angle beams. Early simulations show that one node cannot handle the data rate of all calculated data stream from all sub-arrays, which means that a hierarchical beam forming process will be used.

Is suggested to be implemented as an MPI [6] program per second level beam produced, that launches on all ring buffer nodes and one chosen file writer node. It would, on each ring buffer node, continuously read data from the node-local ring buffer arrays, apply FIR filters on each sample, and then through an MPI_reduce call do a sum of all the subarray input beams with a target on the file writer node. This can also be accelerated by offloading the MPI_reduce into the switch, as mentioned in Section 4.4.

5.3 File writer and prompt computing

The file writer process will take the summed narrow-angle beam results from the second beam former and write these to data files (HDF5-based format suggested) on storage. Instructions for the file sizes, file names and destination folders are in the database written when experiment has been formed. The database also includes necessary metadata information which should be written with the actual data. It is preferred that the HDF5 files will be written to the local SSD buffer on the SBF nodes then transferred to a central location. Local storage should be fast so that exceptional events can be downloaded quickly from ring buffer, so SSD disks are preferred at the site.

The requirements for the file writer processes can be specified by the operating bandwidth (5 MHz or 30 MHz) and the level of data reduction within the second beam former. The overhead in writing

the data to HDF5 files will be negligible as all the experiment-related information is stored in the database and can be added to the HDF5 file system later in the operation center. One narrow angle beam, having 5 MHz bandwidth and two polarizations, is a continuous data stream of 80 MB/s, which is considered very small for any modern SSD disk with write speeds up to 3000 MB/s.

The file writer processes either run on second beam former nodes or on dedicated nodes, downstream of the second beam former. Dedicated nodes can also be used for summing, decimation, data analyzing and event triggering.

5.4 Control

The EISCAT_3D radar transmissions and receive sites will be controlled by the EROS [7] software, used by the current EISCAT radars, re-written for the EISCAT_3D case. This will be defined in a future document “EISCAT_3D Software Requirement Control Document” that is in preparation.

The control software will be built around a distributed database. Isolated programs can work asynchronously and old EROS programs can be added to the cluster easier. The hardware required for the EROS control on each site is not expected to be significant. The computer running EROS must be connected to the 1 Gb/s control network within the site, which also handles timing signals using the White Rabbit synchronization protocol. This network connects EROS mainly to the Pulse and Steering Control Units (PSCU) and FSRUs located in the Sub-Array Containers under the antenna array.

References

- [1] HDF5 Data Format.
<https://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>
- [2] EISCAT 3D FSRU Tender.
<https://www.eiscat.se/business/tenders/e3ds1-fsru/>
- [3] Ongoing FIR filter testing.
<https://wiki.neic.no/int/E3DDSFIRfiltertesting>
- [4] Infiniband Trade Association.
<https://www.infinibandta.org/>
- [5] Omni-Path Architecture.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Omni-Path>
- [6] Message Passing Interface.
<https://www.mcs.anl.gov/research/projects/mpi/>
- [7] EISCAT Scientific Association. EISCAT_3D Radar Control and Monitoring Subsystem Report.
www.sgo.fi/~jussi/e3d/WP7/wp7_2/wp7_report.doc
- [8] FS.com networking equipment.
<https://www.fs.com/de/en/>

Appendix A Cost estimate

A cost estimate is shown here based on the text above. The costs are based on list prices [8] and are made for comparison purposes. A tender in which sufficient ⁵ amounts of equipment is being purchased can result in a 30% reduction in list prices. Given this observation, standardizing the hardware between the sites and buying under a single tender is the strategy that will deliver the most hardware for money. We assume that the number (and therefore the price) of optical cables and connectors from the FSRUs to the input network and site-local computing (i.e. second beam former) is a constant for all options. The output network (Infiniband or other technology after the SBF nodes) is also assumed to be constant, modulo the actual number of SBF nodes. The cost for a 40-port 200 Gb/s Infiniband switch is 20 k€. Infiniband switches are available with 36, 40, or possibly 80 ports.

The network switching equipment (between the FSRUs and SBF nodes) has the following prices:

25 Gbit/s ports	100 Gbit/s ports	Price (k€)	Form
48	12	30	1U
48	6	20	1U
48	4	20	1U
0	32	30	1U
0	64	80	1U

The server costs are based on servers in the Kebnekaise cluster at HPC2N in Umeå (dual CPU, 2.6 GHz, 14 cores) and 384, 768 or 1532 GB RAM (24×16 GB, 32 GB, 64 GB respectively)⁶. This spec includes 2 TB net SSD on raid-5, enough 25 GbE ports, 100 GbE NIC as a stand-in for Infiniband. This is the same specification of server as used in the benchmarking in [3].

RAM (TB)	Price (k€)	Form
0.2	14	2U
0.4	17	2U
0.8	24	2U
1.5	40	2U

The options below, based on the RX sites requirements, correspond to the topologies shown in Figures 3 and 4. An option based on a variation of Figure 4 (Fig 4*) is also provided where the optical connections from the FSRU input network layer to SBF nodes are 100 Gb/s. The option for server RAM closest to 1 TB RAM is used in each case. As can be seen in the table, the cost for each option is dominated by the number of ring buffer nodes. The main cost driver of the ring buffer nodes is the amount of RAM. For example dropping the RAM to 0.4 TB per ring buffer node gives costs of 716, 788 and 874 k€ respectively.

⁵The amount of equipment purchases that trigger discounts varies by supplier and market conditions.

⁶For performance all memory channels should have the same population

Option	Optical Connectors	Switching boxes	SBF nodes	Direct cables	Total
Fig 3	119 × 2 × 25 Gbit/s 36 k€	n/a	40* 960 k€	n/a	80U 996 k€
Fig 4	119 × 2 × 25 Gbit/s 36 k€	2 × 48-25 6-100 Gbit/s 1 × 48-25 12-100 Gbit/s 70 k€	40* 960 k€		83U 1066 k€
Fig 4*	119 × 2 × 100 Gbit/s 72 k€	4 × 32-100 Gbit/s 120 k€	40* 960 k€	23 × 100 Gbit/s 1.8 k€	84U 1154 k€

Appendix B Future outlook

Future hardware outlook

During 2019 new CPU generations from both AMD and Intel will be launched. The AMD processors are expected to bring significant increases in the number and speed of cores, while Intel is expected to bring more modest improvements. Still, a small improvement in the AVX-512 unit could bring big overall performance benefits for our use case.

At the moment AMD has higher main memory bandwidth than Intel server processors, due to four memory channels per processor rather than Intel's three. This difference is foreseen to last at least the next year or two.

There is also likely that new CPUs will bring PCI Express Generation 4, which is a doubling of the data rate for I/O. This might make it possible to pack more 100 Gb/s network interfaces into a single card or possible to use 200 Gb/s Infiniband. The current roadmaps indicate that AMD will launch CPUs with PCIe Gen4 during 2019, and Intel in the middle of 2020.

The biggest cost for the on site computing is the RAM for the ring buffer, which is historically expensive (twice as expensive during 2018 as in 2017). The prices might be going down too.

Newer SSD technologies, either flash or phase change based, might make it possible to build a cheaper ring buffer if they are reliable enough or cheap enough to overprovision sufficiently. Using something else than RAM means moving the data many more times over I/O lanes which probably requires PCIe Gen4 as well as more CPU resources (from HPC2N benchmarks, 2 GB/s disk I/O is enough to saturate a single core, which then is not available for FIR filters).

An interesting possibility for ring buffer storage device is the phase change technology developed by Intel and Micron (OptaneTM). This technology has earlier been used in SATA and NVMe connected storage devices but recently Optane DIMM memory modules has also become available. Optane DIMMs are slower than normal memory modules, but they are able to keep the data permanently in memory. At least in principle, Optane DIMMs could be used in ring buffer instead of normal DIMMs. It is, however, yet unclear what kind of detailed specifications Optane DIMMs have and how competitively they will be priced. In addition, so far Optane DIMMs have been available only for Intel platforms. The use of Optane DIMMs may rule out AMD as a CPU vendor.

The price for 25 Gb/s SFP28 optics modules is likely to drop from today's levels, since this is a very new technology. Rough price parity with 10 Gb/s is expected in a year or two from now, which would cut that cost by almost an order of magnitude.